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Where Small Efforts Quietly Turn Into Something Greater

On the first day of class, I wrote 0.1 on the board. For a few seconds, no one said anything. Some of them leaned forward, others just looked at me, waiting for what was next.

“Ma’am, are we supposed to solve that?” one student asked. “Not yet,” I said. “Tell me first, what is it?” “One-tenth.”

“Parang ang liit, Ma’am,” another one said, and a few of them smiled. “Exactly,” I replied. “It looks small. But what if you add it every day?” They started thinking. I could see some of them counting quietly.

“After ten days?” “One.” “And after a hundred days?” “Ten”, someone said, sounding sure this time. I wrote on the board: Small steps matter.

“Math shows patterns,” I told them. “And sometimes, those patterns are the same ones we see in real life.”

As the weeks went on, the lessons became more challenging. Some students followed right away. Others were quieter, but I knew they were trying.

There was one student who stayed after class almost every time. She would sit there, solving, erasing, then solving again. Sometimes she would just stare at her paper.

One afternoon, she finally said, “Ma’am... hindi ko pa rin gets.” “That’s okay,” I told her. “Try natin ulit.”

We went through the problem slowly. Step by step. No pressure.

The next day, she came back. “Ma’am, I tried again,” she said. And she kept coming back. Hindi man perfect, pero tuloy-tuloy.

Weeks later, I returned their test papers. She looked at hers for a few seconds, then a little longer. “Ma’am... pumasa ako.” “You did,” I said. “And you improved.”

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On the last day of the term, I wrote 0.1 on the board again. This time, they didn't laugh. "It looked small before," I said, "but when you keep adding it, it becomes something."

As they were leaving, one student stopped by the door. "Ma'am," he said, "gets ko na." I smiled. "Ano 'yon?" "It's not about getting it right the first time." He paused. "It's about not giving up."

I nodded. And in that moment, I realized that beyond formulas and numbers, may natutunan sila na mas mahalaga. Na kahit maliit lang sa simula, kapag tinuloy-tuloy mo, lalaki pa rin.